

H-Index / Citation / i10 index Details of

International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT)

ISSN: 0975-3826(online); 0975-4660 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit.html>

Google Scholar Citation

Cited by [VIEW ALL](#)

	All	Since 2015
Citations	6863	5017
h-index	39	31
i10-index	187	151

<https://scholar.google.co.in/citations?hl=en&user=NjtpR1IAAAAJ>

All Since 2015

Citations 6863 5017

h-index 39 31

i10-index 187 151